

A Study on the Impact of Manpower Planning with Special Reference to in Big it at Kumbakonam

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ABSTRACT

BIG IT Every organization operates for the aim of achieving some goals and objective .to facilitate that, corporation's worker and unitize resources like man, money, machine and material. Force coming up with is that the commencement stage in force management, that is formed form coming up with future wants for the staff, coming up with for supply of such staff before taking step to match provide and demand. Force coming up with involves a stock taking of the men and its skills statement the long run demand and provide of skill and medicine approach in order that change may be created to fulfill structure and our country objectives. The essence of the rationale for any imbalance between the provision of and demand for force.

KEYWORDS: fuller and effective utilization, personnel is accessible

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INTRODUCTION

Though the organization of men for managing a purpose is associate old factor, the science of management remains in emergent stage personnel may be primary resources like cash, material etc can't be place to use. Even a completely automatic unit like cash associate unmanned satellite needs personnel a lot of before he learned to use alternative resources.

Objectives of the study:

- To forecast the longer term wants of human resources.
- To ensure fuller and effective utilization of existing human resources.
- To ensure that necessary personnel is accessible as once needed.
- To related human resource coming up with the organization coming up with.

Scope of the study:

- To make the list of current men.
- To check what proportion current men is being utilized
- To find out what proportion men is needed.
- To make the coaching programmers.
- It keeps the record of current force with the organization.
- Assessing the longer term necessities of force for organization objectives.
- To form the force achievement plans.

Limitation of the study:

- The future is unsure.
- Here are several external factors like technological, political, cultural etc...
- Human resource designing is time overwhelming since it collects the entire data concerning the personnel needs of every department.
- It's chic method.

Needs of the study:

Manpower designing may be two-phased method as a result of workforce designing not solely analyses this human resources however conjointly makes workforce forecasts and thereby draw employment programmes. Workforce designing is advantageous firm in following manner. It helps in growth and diversification of business. Shortages and surpluses will be known in order that fact action will be taken where needed. All the accomplishment and choice programmes square measure supported hand designing.

Research methodology:

Research methodology defines the activity of research, hot to precede, how to measure progress, and constitutes success. Methodology is defined as a body of method, rules, and postulates by a discipline.

Research design:

A research design is an arrangement of conditions for collections and analysis of data in manner that aims to

combine relevance to the research purpose. It is which research in conducted. The study is descriptive in nature. Survey is the research design used in the study by taking a sample of employees. The research design used in the study by taking a sample of employees. The researcher adopted this type of research design to gather information from the respondents to evaluate the quality of work life of employees in the organization.

Period of research:

The study is conducted from Jan 2020 to Feb 2020. The total duration of the study is one month.

Sampling procedure:

Sampling:

Sampling design is based on simple random sampling.

Sampling design:

Sampling design based on convenient sampling.

Sampling size:

The sampling size for this study is 100.

Sampling unit:

The sample was collected from the employees **HCL privet limited company Chennai.**

Sampling scale:

- Dichotomous scale
- Category scale
- Interval scale
- Nominal scale

Sources of data:

The two main sources of data used for the present study are primary and secondary data.

Primary data:

Primary data are those which are collected in a fresh way and this data consist of original information collected for specific purpose. The data was collected through structured questionnaire from the employees of HCL.

Secondary data:

Secondary data consist of information that already exist somewhere, have been collected for specific purpose in the study;

The data for this study are collected from books, company, record and website.

Tools used for analysis:

The following statistical tools are used for data analysis.

- Simple percentage analysis
- Chi square
- ANOVA
- Correlation and regression.

1. Chi square test:

Hypothesis 1:

Relationship between the gender and back-up plan when your current employees leaves the organization.

Statistical inference:

C.V = 0.296

T.V = 7.81

C.V < T.V

Not significant

Null hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between gender of the respondents and back-up plan when a current employee leaves the organization.

Alternative hypothesis:

There is a significant relationship between gender of the respondents and back-up plan when a current employee leaves the organization.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Degree of freedom} &= (c-1) (r-1) \\ &= (4-1) (2-1) \\ &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

4 at 5% level of significance.

C.V < T.V

Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted,

Alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Result:

There is no significant relationship between the gender and back-up plan when a current employees leaves the organization.

2. ANOVA:

Null hypothesis:

There is significant ANOVA between gender and back-up plan when a current employees leaves the organization.

Calculate F value is 0.348 and F critical value 0.557 so calculate value is more than the table value so null is rejected.

3. Correlation:

Calculation value is 0.2004 and so I concluded that there is no significant correlation between rate statement and manpower planning should be done sufficiently in advance.

Finding:

- Majority (63%) of the respondents are male.
- Majority (38%) of the respondents belongs to the age group of 25-30 years.
- Majority (47%) of the respondents are monthly income as Rs.15,000 - 25,000.
- Majority (52%) of the respondents are having the education qualification as under graduation.
- Majority (72%) of the respondents are unmarried.
- Majority (28%) of the respondents peoples are research and development department.
- Majority of the respondents are belong to back-up plan when your current employees leaves the organization in yes (96%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to certain department but don't have available team members in yes (75%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to company employees need extra training or education to move up to next level in yes (83%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to availability and competency into account when employees to project in yes (89%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to management will appreciating your good activity in yes (95%)

- Majority of the respondents are belongs to manpower planning should be done sufficiently in advance in yes (81%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to recruitment policy laid down by the organization is partial requirements yes (81%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to performance is give for those who come through a reference is normally (64%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to selection procedure has been done through technical skills to some extent (64%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to involvement of HR in charge in interview panel is partial (48%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to stability employees feel sense of stability in the organization in to some (63%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to HR forecasting help you plan budgets base on you future staffing level in neutral (52%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to utilization of manpower leads to effective cost reduction in neutral (69%)
- Majority of the respondents are belongs to the MPP should incorporate the element of flexibility and element of flexibility and elasticity in neutral (68%)

Suggestion:

It is suggested that the organization should give periodic job rotation based on manpower planning. It is suggested that the organization should give more training to the employees. It is suggested that the organization should give promotions based on experience, because now the promotion are based on experience.

Conclusion:

The manpower planning must introduce to the corporate to enhance true of the corporate. Good planning can bring the corporate raise the income and increase efficiency output.

People are the only resources that can synergies and the only factors is unique in an organization cannot be duplicated by competition.

The study aims at analyzing the manpower planning is done effectively in HCL. Manpower planning should play a major role in transfer of an employee as more than half of the respondents agree that manpower planning plays a role in transfer. This study help the organization to make the manpower planning more effective as it reflect the views and expectations of the employees of HCL.

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